

1 **Near-wall turbulence of semidilute polymer solution flows**
2 **subjected to varying favourable pressure gradient**

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Abstract

High-resolution particle image velocimetry was employed to investigate the near-wall boundary layer (BL) in viscoelastic polymeric flows subjected to pressure gradient (PG) effects in a mesoscale water channel. The flow was driven over a converging surface with varying favourable PG (V-FPG), a flat surface with constant FPG (C-FPG), and a diverging surface with varying adverse PG. This study examines the interplay between viscoelasticity and FPG in shaping BL dynamics. Velocity statistics measured on the channel mid-plane are reported for Newtonian water and non-Newtonian polyacrylamide solutions at concentrations of 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m., with and without PG effects. In fully developed C-FPG polymeric flows, mean streamwise velocity fluctuations increased markedly with concentration, with peak dimensional values enhanced by $\approx 58\%$ and $\approx 87\%$ at the highest flow rates compared to water. Accelerating polymer solution flows exhibited elevated edge-to-mean velocity ratios and relaminarised regions in the converging section due to strong FPGs. Inner-normalised mean velocity profiles deviated from the classical log law depending on the local PG and skin friction. The combination of V-FPG and polymer viscoelasticity strongly suppressed Reynolds shear stresses, with peak dimensional values reduced by $\approx 80\%$ and $\approx 89\%$ in accelerating 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m. flows relative to water. These findings provide new insights into the coupled effects of PGs and viscoelasticity on wall-bounded turbulence, offering guidance for improved numerical modelling and engineering design in complex flow systems.

7 I. INTRODUCTION

8 In many industrial and natural flows, turbulent boundary layers develop over complex,
9 non-flat surfaces, where changes in wall geometry induce local acceleration ($\partial U_e/\partial s > 0$)
10 with a varying favourable pressure gradient (V-FPG, $\partial P_e/\partial s < 0$), or deceleration ($\partial U_e/\partial s <$
11 0) with a varying adverse pressure gradient (V-APG, $\partial P_e/\partial s > 0$). Here, $U_e(s)$ and $P_e(s)$
12 denote the velocity and pressure at the boundary-layer (BL) edge along the wall-parallel
13 coordinate s . In contrast, fully developed channel flows experience no streamwise acceler-
14 ation ($\partial U_e/\partial s = 0$) and are driven downstream by a constant favourable pressure gradient
15 (C-FPG).

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16 Such pressure-gradient turbulent flows are not only of academic interest but also arise in
17 engineering practice. A notable example is found in inflow control devices (ICDs) employed
18 in steam-assisted gravity drainage (SAGD) for oil extraction, where steam injection reduces
19 bitumen viscosity to enable gravity-driven production [1]. ICDs, widely deployed in Cana-
20 dian SAGD wells [2], improve recovery by delaying water and gas breakthroughs. However,
21 constrictions such as orifices and nozzles, while suppressing unwanted phases, can produce
22 large pressure drops that induce cavitation, choke the flow, and reduce overall efficiency.

23 ICDs involve complex multi-scale, multiphysics, and multiphase flow interactions, moti-
24 vating the need for advanced designs that improve efficiency and mitigate cavitation erosion.
25 Achieving this requires a deeper understanding of turbulence control and cavitation suppres-
26 sion strategies. Previous work [3] showed that drag-reducing polymer additives can effec-
27 tively reduce cavitation in a standard ICD nozzle. Building on this foundation, the present
28 study investigates the combined influence of flow acceleration and polymer viscoelasticity
29 on near-wall turbulence in pressure-gradient-driven channels.

30 Non-zero pressure gradients generate non-equilibrium BLs whose turbulent statistics de-
31 viate from those of fully developed C-FPG flows. Under both FPG and APG, the BL often
32 exhibits a two-layer structure: an inner layer strongly influenced by the PG with minimal
33 curvature effects, and an outer layer resembling a free shear layer [4–6]. Unlike canonical
34 C-FPG flows over smooth flat surfaces, which exhibit directionally invariant turbulence,
35 pressure-gradient-driven flows are locally varying and more complex. The present work ex-
36 tends prior studies of accelerating flows and viscoelastic effects to elucidate these coupled
37 dynamics.

38 **A. Effect of acceleration**

39 Turbulent BLs subjected to strong FPG and APG, as found over airfoils, ship hulls, or
40 turbine blades, exhibit complex behaviour influenced by the accumulated turbulence history,
41 often referred to as the “history effect” of the PG [7, 8]. Despite their practical importance,
42 pressure-gradient turbulent BLs remain relatively underexplored, warranting further exper-
43 imental and numerical investigation. Early work by Narasimha and Sreenivasan [9] and
44 Sreenivasan [10] showed that strong acceleration or mechanisms that dissipate turbulent
45 energy can induce relaminarisation, where turbulent statistics deviate markedly from the

46 classical logarithmic velocity profile.

47 The onset of relaminarisation is commonly characterised by a non-dimensional FPG pa-
 48 rameter, $\Delta_p \approx -5 \times 10^{-3}$ [11], defined as

$$\Delta_p(s) = \frac{\nu_w(s)}{\rho u_\tau^3(s)} \frac{dP_e(s)}{ds}, \quad (1)$$

49 where ν_w is the wall kinematic viscosity, ρ the fluid density, and $u_\tau = \sqrt{\tau_w/\rho}$ the friction
 50 velocity based on local wall shear stress $\tau_w(s)$. Further acceleration reduces Δ_p , producing
 51 non-equilibrium flows and BL thinning; complete relaminarisation occurs near $\Delta_p \approx -18 \times$
 52 10^{-3} [11]. Other criteria include the acceleration parameter

$$K(s) = \frac{\nu_w(s)}{U_e^2(s)} \frac{dU_e(s)}{ds}, \quad (2)$$

53 with a threshold of $K \approx 3 \times 10^{-6}$ [9, 12], and the non-dimensional shear stress gradient

$$\Delta_\tau(s) = \frac{\nu_w(s)}{\rho u_\tau^3(s)} \frac{\Delta\tau(s)}{n_v}, \quad (3)$$

54 where $\Delta\tau = \tau_v(s) - \tau_w(s)$ and n_v is the viscous sublayer thickness. Relaminarisation onset
 55 has been reported near $\Delta_\tau \approx -9 \times 10^{-3}$ [13]. As turbulence vanishes, the logarithmic layer
 56 disappears [5], and Reynolds stress contributions to the mean flow become negligible [10].

57 Direct numerical simulations (DNS) by Balin and Jansen [4] over a Gaussian bump re-
 58 vealed mean velocity profiles rising above the logarithmic law under strong acceleration,
 59 consistent with experimental observations [14] and prior simulations [15]. Their results
 60 showed quasi-relaminarised regions with attenuated Reynolds stresses and reduced turbu-
 61 lent production. Similarly, Volino [16] reported suppression of wake and Reynolds stresses
 62 under strong FPG in channel flows with ramped pressure gradients, supported by particle
 63 image velocimetry (PIV) measurements.

64 B. Effect of viscoelasticity

65 While drag reduction (DR) in polymer solutions has been widely studied in fully devel-
 66 oped C-FPG channel and pipe flows, comparatively little is known about BL turbulence in
 67 polymeric flows subjected to spatially varying PGs. In dilute polymer solutions, turbulent
 68 drag can be reduced substantially, with the degree of DR depending on polymer molecular
 69 weight, concentration, and flow rate [17, 18]. A key finding by Virk *et al.* [18] was the

70 existence of a maximum drag reduction (MDR) asymptote, beyond which no further DR
 71 occurs. He proposed the following mean velocity profile for MDR conditions:

$$\langle U_s \rangle^+ = 11.7 \ln(n^+) - 17.0, \quad (4)$$

72 valid for $n^+ > 11.6$ in smooth C-FPG pipe flows, with ‘+’ denoting inner scaling by the
 73 friction velocity u_τ and viscous length scale $\lambda_v = \nu_w/u_\tau$. Virk also identified three wall-
 74 normal zones in DR flows: the viscous, interactive, and Newtonian plug layers. For moderate
 75 DR ($DR \leq 40\%$), the mean velocity retains the Newtonian slope but shifts upward, while
 76 for $DR \gtrsim 40\%$ the Newtonian log-law vanishes and the velocity profile approaches the MDR
 77 asymptote [19].

78 Drag reduction is typically quantified as

$$DR(\%) = \left(1 - \frac{c_{f,s}}{c_{f,0}}\right) \times 100, \quad (5)$$

79 where the skin-friction coefficient is

$$c_{f,b} = \frac{\tau_w}{0.5\rho U_b^2}, \quad (6)$$

80 with U_b the bulk velocity and subscripts s and 0 denoting polymer solution and pure solvent,
 81 respectively. The buffer layer thickens with increasing DR [20–22].

82 Three main hypotheses have been proposed to explain the onset of DR in dilute polymer
 83 solutions. (a) Time criterion: DR occurs when the polymer relaxation time t_R exceeds
 84 the viscous timescale $t_v = \nu_w/u_\tau^2$, i.e. $We_i = t_R/t_v > 1$ [23–25]; DNS by Min *et al.* [21]
 85 suggested onset near $We_i \approx 6$. (b) Elongation viscosity: polymers undergo a coil–stretch
 86 transition in high-strain regions, enhancing extensional viscosity and damping small-scale
 87 eddies [25, 26]; this mechanism, however, does not fully explain stress deficits or onset
 88 [27]. (c) Elastic theory: extended polymer chains absorb near-wall energy and re-release it
 89 into outer regions when $We_i > 1$, suppressing wall-normal and spanwise fluctuations while
 90 enhancing streamwise turbulence [21, 28–31].

91 Experimental studies support these mechanisms. For instance, Warholic *et al.* [32] re-
 92 ported DR of 41% and 51% with 1.25 p.p.m. and 50 p.p.m. copolymer solutions of polyacry-
 93 lamide (PAM) and water, showing strong damping of wall-normal fluctuations and ejections.
 94 Although streamwise Reynolds stresses $\langle u_s^2 \rangle$ remained similar to Newtonian values, their
 95 inner-scaled counterparts $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$ increased significantly. At $DR = 55\%$, $\tau_{w,PAM} \approx 0.54 \tau_{w,water}$,

96 leading to $\langle u_s^2 \rangle_{\text{PAM}}^+ \approx 1.85 \langle u_s^2 \rangle_{\text{water}}^+$. Wall-normal and shear stresses, when scaled with New-
97 tonian $u_{\tau,0}$, were strongly suppressed.

98 Complementary numerical studies have clarified the role of polymer stress models. DNS
99 with the Oldroyd-B model [21] showed decreasing near-wall streamwise r.m.s. fluctuations
100 (scaled by $u_{\tau,0}$) with increasing We_i , alongside suppression of wall-normal and spanwise
101 fluctuations, consistent with experiments [20, 32, 33]. Using the FENE-P model, Ptasinski
102 *et al.* [31] demonstrated that streamwise turbulence intensities initially increase with DR
103 but decrease at MDR, while polymer stresses contributed $\sim 40\%$ of the total shear. Energy
104 transfer from the mean flow to elastic storage by the polymers was identified as a central
105 mechanism at MDR.

106 In addition to their elastic properties, many drag-reducing polymers, such as the PAM
107 used in this study, exhibit significant shear-thinning behaviour. While shear-thinning mod-
108 ifies the mean velocity profile by reducing the effective viscosity in high-shear near-wall
109 regions, it is a distinct physical phenomenon from the elastic mechanisms, such as energy
110 absorption during the coil-stretch transition, that lead to the suppression of turbulent fluc-
111 tuations. Elucidating the interplay between these two effects is critical for interpreting flow
112 statistics in non-equilibrium boundary layers.

113 C. Summary

114 A turbulent flow subjected to a streamwise PG develops a BL on the wall, with turbulence
115 statistics that are spatially dependent and do not necessarily conform to the canonical
116 turbulence observed in fully developed C-FPG flows. The interaction between the inner-
117 layer turbulence and the large-scale motions of the outer layer in PG flows, along with
118 their complex local and global effects on turbulence statistics and the non-trivial history
119 dependence, poses significant challenges for both experimental and numerical investigations.
120 Meanwhile, numerous studies have examined turbulence in fully developed viscoelastic dilute
121 solution flows within channels. Although the precise mechanism by which polymer additives
122 induce DR remains debated, both PIV measurements and DNS consistently show that DR
123 agents thicken the buffer layer, enhance streamwise turbulence, and attenuate wall-normal
124 and spanwise turbulence intensities.

125 The influence of polymer additives on turbulence in flows subjected to strong PGs remains

126 largely unexplored. Prior studies on Newtonian flows have shown that a strong FPG re-
 127 duces turbulence intensities, induces relaminarisation, and yields a thinner BL. The present
 128 study aims to elucidate the physical mechanisms governing the development of turbulent
 129 BLs under the combined effects of viscoelasticity and flow acceleration. To the authors’
 130 knowledge, no existing literature directly addresses this phenomenon. To investigate it, PIV
 131 was employed to capture high-resolution velocity fields at the mid-span of a bumped chan-
 132 nel, where a strong FPG developed and polymer additives, acting as DR agents, modified
 133 the flow characteristics.

134 The experimental methodology is detailed in § II. The mean flow features and turbulence
 135 statistics are presented in § III A for fully developed C-FPG Newtonian and non-Newtonian
 136 flows, and in § III B for flows subjected to a V-FPG. A rigorous uncertainty analysis and the
 137 statistical convergence of the main turbulence quantities are provided in the Supplementary
 138 Material.

139 II. EXPERIMENTAL SYSTEM

140 A. Bump geometry

141 A bumped smooth wall profile was designed to examine non-equilibrium flow subjected
 142 to streamwise-varying favourable and adverse pressure gradients. This study focuses only
 143 on the effect of V-FPG flows. The channel geometry is illustrated in figure 1. It comprises
 144 a converging-diverging bump on the channel’s lower wall to exert successive favourable and
 145 adverse pressure gradients on the flow. The flow path has an inlet height of $h_{\text{in}} = 8$ mm. The
 146 bump profile increases in height with a constant slope over $L_c = 2.3$ mm at a convergence
 147 angle of $\theta_c = 60^\circ$ to produce a bump height of $h_b = 2$ mm, which is extended for $L_b = 3.4$ mm
 148 downstream, with a zero slope. Fillets of radii $r_c = r_d = 1$ mm were applied to the
 149 convergence profile to make its start and end lines tangent to the horizontal flow path.

150 The bump profile begins to decrease in height from the origin of the coordinate system,
 151 as shown in figure 1, with a constant slope and a divergence angle of $\theta_d = 12^\circ$ over a length
 152 of $L_d = 11.5$ mm, until it transitions to the downstream flat surface. Dean [34] proposed
 153 that a minimum aspect ratio (AR) of ≈ 7 in rectangular channels is required to minimise
 154 significant 3D disturbances and assume a predominantly 2D central flow. In this study, the

Figure 1. Main variables associated with bump geometry. The channel body is shaded.

channel width is $w = 60$ mm, yielding a minimum $AR = w/h_{\text{in}} = 7.5$ at the inlet.

B. Flow facility

As illustrated schematically in figure 2, a flow facility was built to investigate the BL dynamics of water and semidilute viscoelastic polymer solution flows. Drag-reducing polyacrylamide (PAM) additives (BASF SE; Germany) were used to create 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m. non-Newtonian solutions. The entry length required for the turbulent flow to fully develop was approximated using the equation [35]: $L_{\text{en}} = 1.36 D_h Re_{D_h}^{0.25}$. At the channel's inlet, $D_h = 14.12$ mm and flow rate was $15 \text{ L min}^{-1} < \dot{V} < 25 \text{ L min}^{-1}$. Hence, $182 \text{ mm} < L_{\text{en}} < 207 \text{ mm}$. The total inlet length was chosen to be ≈ 220 mm to ensure generating an initial fully developed turbulent flow field.

A contraction of 85 mm in length transformed the flow path's circular cross-section into a rectangular entrance of dimensions $8 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$. A honeycomb was used to straighten the incoming flow, featuring a hexagonal distribution pattern with hollow sections of circumscribed circle diameter of 1.7 mm. The contraction and diffuser sections, honeycomb, test section, and bump profile were fabricated using low-force stereolithography technology (Form 3; Formlabs Inc.). The bump profile can be easily detached from the test section and replaced with different shapes to create various configurations. The bump surface was polished using ultra-fine micro-grit sandpapers, followed by applying a plastic polish (7100 Plastic Polish Kit; NOVUS Plastic Polish) to remove micro-scratches and make the surface smooth. Two transparent acrylic windows were installed on both sides of the channel to provide optical access to the internal flow. The flow exited the test section through a diffuser section, identical to the contraction, and returned to a reservoir with a capacity of 20 L.

Figure 2. Experimental facility and optical setup (top view). Dimensions in mm unless noted; not to scale. Labels indicate main components.

177 C. Flow rheology

178 The PAM powder was gently mixed with tap water in a 500 mL glass beaker using
 179 a stirrer (1103; Jenway) for two hours to produce a uniform concentrated solution. The
 180 master solution was gradually added to the circulating water flow using a port located at
 181 the pump's discharge line. Before entering the main test section, the solution was circulated
 182 moderately through the bypass line for fifteen minutes to generate a uniform semidilute
 183 mixture. As explained in Azadi and Nobes [3], mechanical degradation was inevitable in the
 184 long run, where it was reported that the measured instantaneous $DR\%$ dropped by only 5%
 185 after ≈ 8 minutes. In the current study, each PIV recording took ≈ 11 s (see Section IID),
 186 for which the degradation rate was inconsequential.

187 Several samples were taken online from the flowing solutions during the experiments,
 188 using a sampling port shown in figure 2. The rheological characteristics of the samples were

Table I. CY model coefficients for the tested PAM solutions.

C_s (p.p.m.)	μ_0 (mPas)	μ_∞ (mPas)	λ_t (s)	n	a	r	R
200	8.01	1.39	2.29	0.58	3.52	1.0000	0.9999
400	8.40	1.53	0.16	0.53	0.73	0.9993	0.9987

189 examined using a rotational rheometer (Kinexus lab+; NETZSCH-Gerätebau GmbH) with
190 a double gap geometry (DG25). The internal height of the bob was 57.5 mm, and its internal
191 and external diameters were 23 mm and 25 mm, respectively. The cup had a diameter of
192 26.25 mm and an insert diameter of 22 mm. For each sample, three shear-rate controlled
193 tests were performed at 22 °C. Figure 3(a) illustrates the variation of the fluid viscosity, μ ,
194 with shear strain rate, $\dot{\gamma}$, for water and the two PAM solutions. To explicitly define $\mu(\dot{\gamma})$
195 for each shear-thinning PAM solution, the Carreau-Yasuda (CY) model [36] was fitted to
196 the rheology data, and the corresponding profiles are plotted in figure 3(a) as dashed lines.
197 The CY model is defined as:

$$\mu(\dot{\gamma}) = \mu_\infty + (\mu_0 - \mu_\infty)[1 + (\lambda_t \dot{\gamma})^a]^{(n-1)/a}, \quad (7)$$

198 where μ_0 and μ_∞ are the zero and infinite shear viscosities. Here, λ_t is a time constant, n
199 is the power-law index, and a is a constant parameter suggested by Yasuda *et al.* [36]. The
200 model coefficients for each solution are listed in table I. For the obtained correlations, the
201 Pearson correlation coefficient r [37], was more than 0.9992 and the coefficient of determi-
202 nation R , was larger than 0.9985, validating the viability of the obtained correlations for
203 viscosity estimation from the shear-strain rate.

204 Oscillatory frequency sweep measurements were conducted at a constant strain amplitude
205 of 1 % using the same bob and cup geometry. Figure 3(b,c) shows the frequency-dependent
206 storage modulus, $G'(\omega)$, and loss modulus, $G''(\omega)$, for the 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m. PAM
207 solutions. The crossover point between G' and G'' , highlighted by an orange-red circle
208 in figure 3(b,c), defines the characteristic angular frequency, ω_c . At this transition, the
209 viscoelastic response shifts from a viscous-dominated regime ($\omega < \omega_c$, $G' < G''$) to an
210 elastic-dominated regime, known as the rubbery plateau ($\omega > \omega_c$, $G' > G''$). The longest
211 relaxation time of the solution is inversely related to ω_c , given by $t_{\max} = 2\pi/\omega_c$. Based on
212 this relation, $t_{\max} = 93.19$ ms and $t_{\max} = 286.66$ ms were estimated for the 200 p.p.m. and
213 400 p.p.m. solutions, respectively.

Figure 3. (a) Shear viscosity, μ , plotted against shear rate, $\dot{\gamma}$, for the tested PAM solutions, with dashed lines representing Carreau–Yasuda (CY) model fits to the data. (b, c) Elastic modulus, G' (blue), and viscous modulus, G'' (black), as functions of angular frequency, ω , for the 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m. solutions, respectively. The strain amplitude was fixed at 1 % and the temperature held constant at 22 °C. The crossover point of $G'(\omega)$ and $G''(\omega)$, marked with an orange-red circle, indicates the critical frequency, ω_c , from which the maximum relaxation time is given by $t_{max} = 2\pi/\omega_c$. Vertical error bars show the standard deviation from three independent measurements.

214 D. Velocimetry

215 Planar PIV was employed to measure the mid-span flow field ($z = 0$) over the top wall
 216 under both C-FPG and V-FPG conditions (figure 4). A high-speed camera (Phantom VEO
 217 710) operated in frame-straddling mode acquired 11 000 uncorrelated image pairs per case,
 218 using a time delay of $\Delta t_{PIV} = 40\text{--}60$ μs to limit particle displacements to below 10 pixels.
 219 The flow was illuminated by a high-current LED source (iLA.LPS v3) with 1.5 μs pulses, and
 220 seeded with 10 μm polystyrene particles. A zoom lens with magnification $M \approx 3.4$ yielded
 221 focused particle image sizes of 2–4 pixels. Calibration was performed using a micro-target
 222 plate and a third-order polynomial mapping with r.m.s. error < 0.15 pixels.

223 Image processing involved background subtraction, intensity normalisation, and multi-
 224 pass cross-correlation with circular and elongated interrogation windows (48×48 to 32×32
 225 pixels, 50–75% overlap), aligned with the flow direction. Outliers were removed using the
 226 universal detection method of Westerweel and Scarano [38], affecting less than 1% of vectors.
 227 The final velocity fields were interpolated onto a 77×113 grid. Further experimental details
 228 are provided in Azadi [39].

Figure 4. General representation of the flow path. Turbulent regions investigated experimentally are marked by light orange rectangles with dashed borders. BL thickness profiles across the channel for three water flows were also estimated using two-dimensional simulations with a $k-\epsilon$ turbulence model, near-wall resolution, and approximately 8 million mesh cells (SOLIDWORKS, 2023, Dassault Systèmes). Solid and dashed lines represent BL thicknesses based on the generalised [40] and classical definitions of U_e , respectively. Black, orange, and blue curves correspond to bulk velocities of $U_b = 0.73 \text{ m s}^{-1}$, 0.99 m s^{-1} , and 1.10 m s^{-1} . C-FPG and V-FPG refer to constant and varying favourable pressure gradients. The inlet channel height is $h_{in} = 8 \text{ mm}$, with local wall-parallel and wall-normal coordinates denoted by (s, \mathbf{e}_s) and (n, \mathbf{e}_n) .

229 III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

230 A. Fully-developed, constant pressure gradient flow

231 Table II lists the main BL parameters of the fully developed C-FPG turbulent flows of
 232 water and PAM solutions under three different flow rates denoted by Case I-III. For the
 233 water cases, friction Reynolds numbers in the range $Re_\tau = 200\text{--}286$ were examined, where
 234 $Re_\tau = u_\tau \delta / \nu_w$ denotes the friction Reynolds number. These results correspond to the C-FPG
 235 interrogation region highlighted in figure 4.

236 The experimentally estimated BL thicknesses are approximately equal to the half-channel
 237 height of 4 mm, with a maximum relative deviation of 1.5% observed for the water flow at
 238 $Re_\tau = 245$. This deviation arises from uncertainties in the velocity measurements, which
 239 are discussed in Supplementary Material. As Re_τ increases in the water flow, the ratios of
 240 the displacement thickness to the BL thickness, δ^*/δ , and the momentum thickness to the
 241 BL thickness, θ/δ , remain nearly constant at $\delta^*/\delta \approx 0.14$ and $\theta/\delta \approx 0.10$.

Table II. Main bulk and near-wall BL parameters of the fully-developed C-FPG turbulent flow of the working fluids. Measurements location is highlighted in figure 4.

Parameter	Unit	Case I			Case II			Case III		
C_s	p.p.m.	0	200	400	0	200	400	0	200	400
μ_w	mPa s	0.91	1.60	1.63	0.91	1.58	1.60	0.91	1.57	1.59
U_b	m s^{-1}	0.73	0.77	0.75	0.93	0.99	0.97	1.10	1.20	1.16
U_e	m s^{-1}	0.84	0.93	0.97	1.07	1.22	1.23	1.25	1.49	1.48
Re_b		6 403	3 725	3 819	8 084	5 043	4 874	9 644	6 158	5 995
Re_e		3 701	2 229	2 451	4 638	3 100	3 089	5 461	3 830	3 815
$Re_\tau = \delta^+$		200	122	108	245	139	124	286	154	141
δ	mm	3.99	3.85	4.15	3.94	4.02	4.03	3.99	4.03	4.10
δ^*/δ		0.14	0.18	0.24	0.14	0.20	0.22	0.13	0.21	0.23
θ/δ		0.10	0.11	0.13	0.10	0.12	0.13	0.09	0.13	0.13
H		1.43	1.61	1.80	1.40	1.68	1.74	1.35	1.66	1.77
G		5.52	6.94	10.09	5.46	8.99	10.58	4.96	9.91	11.74
$\dot{\gamma}_w \times 10^{-3}$	s^{-1}	2.29	1.60	1.11	3.50	1.90	1.52	4.66	2.28	1.88
τ_w	Pa	2.09	2.56	1.81	3.19	3.00	2.44	4.24	3.58	2.98
u_τ	mm s^{-1}	45.7	50.6	42.6	56.5	54.8	49.4	65.1	59.8	54.5
λ_v	μm	19.9	31.6	38.4	16.1	28.9	32.5	14.0	26.3	29.1
L_s^+		178	108	92	219	126	112	253	137	123
L_n^+		262	160	135	322	186	165	373	202	182
$\Delta s^+ = \Delta n^+$		2.3	1.4	1.2	2.9	1.7	1.5	3.3	1.8	1.6
$c_{f,b} \times 10^3$		8.16	9.34	9.29	7.70	8.66	8.74	7.37	8.24	8.30
$DR\%$			-5.3	20.0		19.4	31.7		30.9	38.8

242 The shape factor, $H = \delta^*/\theta$, and the Clauser (or defect) shape factor, G , exhibit relative
243 reductions of approximately 5% and 10%, respectively, with increasing mean velocity. The
244 defect shape factor is defined as $G = (U_e/u_\tau)(1 - H^{-1})$ [41, 42].

245 Dean [34] showed that in a fully developed 2D Newtonian turbulent channel flow,

$$(U_e/U_b)_{\text{Dean}} = 1.28 Re_b^{-0.0116}, \quad (8)$$

$$c_{f, \text{Dean}} = 0.073 Re_b^{-0.25}, \quad (9)$$

247 where $Re_b = U_b(2\delta)/\nu_w$ is the bulk Reynolds number. The measured ratios U_e/U_b of water
 248 are in close agreement with those predicted by equation 8. The determined U_e/U_b values in
 249 the PAM solutions are generally higher than those given by equation 8, indicating that the
 250 polymer additives modify the structure of the mean velocity profile. Water flow was tested
 251 at three flow rates with $6.4 \times 10^3 < Re_b < 9.6 \times 10^3$, and PAM solutions were tested at
 252 $3.7 \times 10^3 < Re_b < 6.0 \times 10^3$.

253 The shear strain rates reported in table II were determined via two complementary ap-
 254 proaches. For cases with sufficient near-wall spatial resolution, a linear least-squares fit was
 255 applied to the mean velocity profiles within the viscous sublayer ($n^+ < 5$). In cases where
 256 near-wall data were limited, strain rates were derived from pressure drop measurements. For
 257 experimental runs where both methods were applicable, the results showed good agreement
 258 with discrepancies below 7%; in these instances, the values obtained from the velocity profile
 259 fits were adopted for consistency.

260 The wall shear viscosity of each PAM flow, $\mu_w(\dot{\gamma}_w)$, was determined from the correspond-
 261 ing CY model, as discussed in § IIC. Using the estimated $\dot{\gamma}_w$ and the measured μ_w , the mean
 262 wall shear stress, τ_w , was calculated for each flow as $\tau_w = \mu_w \dot{\gamma}_w$, where $\dot{\gamma}_w = (\partial \langle U_s \rangle / \partial n)_{n_w=0}$.

263 For experiments conducted at a constant flow rate, the drag reduction percentage was
 264 evaluated from equation 5 as $DR\% = 1 - (\tau_{w,s}/\tau_{w,0})$, where the equivalent Newtonian wall
 265 shear stress, $\tau_{w,0}$, was computed specifically for each polymeric flow case using the corre-
 266 sponding measured bulk velocity, U_b . This normalisation accounts for the slight fluctuations
 267 in U_b observed across tests (table I). Notably, while most cases exhibited significant DR, the
 268 200 p.p.m. solution at the lowest flow rate ($\tau_w = 2.56$ Pa) resulted in a drag increase of
 269 5.3%. This phenomenon of drag enhancement at low Re is likely attributed to the onset of
 270 elasto-inertial turbulence, where the energy expenditure associated with polymer stretching
 271 and elastic instabilities outweighs the turbulence suppression observed at higher inertia [43].

272 Previous studies support the idea that transition behaviour is concentration-dependent.
 273 Chandra *et al.* [44] observed that while dilute solutions (50-100 p.p.m.) increased the tran-
 274 sitional bulk Reynolds number to $Re_{b,t} \approx 2500$, higher concentrations such as 300 p.p.m.
 275 reduced $Re_{b,t}$ to values close to Newtonian flows ($Re_{b,t} \approx 2000$). Their results show a fur-
 276 ther decrease in $Re_{b,t}$ for even higher concentrations (500-800 p.p.m.). Hence, moderate

277 concentrations like 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m., as used in this study, might exhibit early
 278 turbulence onset at lower Re_b values, consistent with our observations. Velocity fields at
 279 transitional Reynolds numbers were not measured in the present experiments.

280 1. Newtonian flow

281 Mean turbulent flow statistics were obtained by averaging $N_t = 11\,000$ instantaneous PIV
 282 fields. The analysis, presented in the Supplementary Material, confirms good statistical con-
 283 vergence of the mean velocity and Reynolds stresses in both Newtonian and non-Newtonian
 284 flows. The mean wall-parallel velocity profiles of the C-FPG water flow, normalised by the
 285 corresponding inner scales, $\langle U_s \rangle^+$, are plotted in figure 5(a) against the inner-normalised
 286 wall-normal coordinate, n^+ . For reference, the linear profile, $\langle U_s \rangle^+ = n^+$, and the standard
 287 logarithmic law of the wall, $\langle U_s \rangle^+ = (1/0.41) \ln(n^+) + 5.5$, are included in figure 5(a) as black
 288 dashed lines. As demonstrated, the inner-normalised mean velocity profiles collapse onto a
 289 consistent trend and follow the law of the wall within the logarithmic region ($n^+ > 30$).

290 The wall-normal variation of the inner-normalised mean Reynolds stresses for the C-FPG
 291 water flow is shown in figure 5(b). These profiles were corrected for measurement noise bias
 292 [45]. Regions where the uncertainty of the mean Reynolds stresses exceeded 10% ($n^+ \lesssim 10$)
 293 have been excluded from the analysis.

294 The $\langle u_s u_n \rangle^+$ profiles exhibit a minimum value of ≈ -0.7 at $n^+ \approx 100$. The streamwise
 295 Reynolds stress, $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$, reaches its maximum at $n^+ \approx 15$, followed by a gradual decline and
 296 a plateau in the range $50 < n^+ < 90$. Beyond $n^+ > 100$, the $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$ profiles decrease with a
 297 steeper gradient compared to the near-wall region. An increase in Re_τ results in an upward
 298 shift of the $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$ profiles across the wall-normal domain. The wall-normal Reynolds stresses,
 299 $\langle u_n^2 \rangle^+$, exhibit a broad plateau around $n^+ \approx 100$, which also marginally shifts upward with
 300 increasing Re_τ . The velocity and Reynolds stress profiles obtained for the C-FPG turbulent
 301 water flow are in close agreement with those of canonical channel flows.

302 2. Non-Newtonian flow

303 Figure 6(a,b) illustrates the distribution of the mean wall-parallel velocity for the fully-
 304 developed 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m. PAM solution flows, normalised by their respective

Figure 5. Inner-normalised turbulence statistics for fully developed C-FPG turbulent water flow: (a) mean wall-parallel velocity, $\langle U_s \rangle^+$, and (b) Reynolds shear stress, $\langle u_s u_n \rangle^+$, streamwise Reynolds stress, $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$, and wall-normal Reynolds stress, $\langle u_n^2 \rangle^+$, as functions of the inner-normalised wall-normal coordinate, n^+ , at three different Re_τ values (see table II). The horizontal axis, n^+ , is logarithmic. Vertical error bars denote the standard deviation from streamwise averaging. For clarity, error bars in panel (b) are shown for every tenth data point.

305 inner scales. The linear and logarithmic laws of the wall, along with Virk’s asymptote,
 306 $\langle U_s \rangle^+ = 11.7 \ln(n^+) - 17$, are shown as dashed black lines. The velocity profiles collapse in
 307 the viscous sublayer, following the linear law of the wall closely. However, away from the wall,
 308 the profiles deviate from the standard Newtonian logarithmic law. This deviation toward the
 309 ultimate profile becomes more pronounced at higher velocities and polymer concentrations.
 310 For both tested solutions with $DR\% < 40\%$, none of the profiles fully converge to the
 311 ultimate profile. As Re_τ increases, and consequently DR intensifies, the slope of the velocity
 312 profiles in the outer layer steepens, approaching the ultimate profile.

313 The distributions of the mean Reynolds shear stress in the boundary layer for the
 314 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m. solutions, normalised by the inner scales of the equivalent
 315 Newtonian flows ($u_{\tau,0}$), are shown for three different Re_τ in figure 7(a,b). The peak magni-
 316 tudes of the polymeric flows increase with Re_τ , while their wall-normal locations shift toward
 317 higher n_0^+ . Compared to the Newtonian water flows, the Reynolds shear stress profiles in

Figure 6. Inner-normalised mean wall-parallel velocity, $\langle U_s \rangle^+$, as a function of the inner-normalised wall-normal coordinate, n^+ , for fully developed C-FPG PAM solution flows: (a) 200 p.p.m. and (b) 400 p.p.m., each at three different Re_τ values (see table II). The linear and logarithmic laws of the wall, together with Virk’s ultimate velocity profile [18], are included as dashed black lines.

318 the polymer solutions are substantially suppressed; for instance, a reduction of 78% in the
 319 peak magnitude is observed at the highest flow rate.

320 Compared to the Newtonian baseline (figure 5b and solid lines in figure 7a,b), the peak
 321 locations of the $\langle u_s^2 \rangle_0^+$ profiles for the 200 p.p.m. solution shift away from the wall, where
 322 the profiles exhibit a broad plateau rather than a distinct peak. A similar outward shift
 323 is observed for the 400 p.p.m. cases, with the onset of the plateau varying across Re_τ .
 324 The lack of collapse among the PAM solution profiles under this scaling indicates that the
 325 enhancement of wall-parallel turbulence intensity is not solely a result of reduced wall shear
 326 stress, but a fundamental change in the turbulence structure. At the highest flow rate, the
 327 peak streamwise intensities for the 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m. solutions are amplified by
 328 factors of 1.8 and 2.2, respectively, relative to the Newtonian flow.

329 The mean wall-normal Reynolds stress profiles collapse in the near-wall region before
 330 diverging marginally in the outer layer. These values increase up to approximately one-
 331 quarter of the channel height, beyond which a plateau with a reduced gradient extends
 332 toward the centerline. The addition of long-chain polymers significantly attenuates the

333 wall-normal Reynolds stresses, resulting in a reduction by a factor of 0.4 compared to
 334 the water flow. This suppression of wall-normal fluctuations, coupled with the streamwise
 335 enhancement, is consistent with the decoupling of the velocity fluctuation components in
 336 drag-reduced flows.

337 The observed enhancement of streamwise intensity $\langle u_s^2 \rangle_0^+$ and the simultaneous suppres-
 338 sion of wall-normal intensity $\langle u_n^2 \rangle_0^+$ and shear stress $\langle u_s u_n \rangle_0^+$ signify a significant reorgani-
 339 sation of the turbulent structures. In the presence of polymers, the stretching of molecules
 340 by the mean shear suppresses the vertical 'bursting' process and dampens the wall-normal
 341 velocity components. While the shear-thinning nature of the PAM solution reduces the local
 342 wall viscosity μ_w (as accounted for in table II), this viscous modification is secondary to the
 343 elastic energy redistribution. This results in a redistribution of turbulent kinetic energy
 344 into the streamwise direction, leading to the formation of highly elongated, high-intensity
 345 streamwise streaks [29, 33]. This structural change explains why the streamwise fluctuations
 346 remain significantly higher than those of the Newtonian case, even when compared using
 347 the equivalent Newtonian inner scaling.

348 The use of the Carreau-Yasuda model to determine the local wall shear viscosity $\mu_w(\dot{\gamma}_w)$
 349 ensures that the reported reductions in turbulent stress are interpreted through a framework
 350 that accounts for shear-thinning. This distinction is critical; while shear-thinning modifies
 351 the viscous sublayer by reducing local resistance, the massive collapse of Reynolds shear
 352 stress and the simultaneous 2.2-fold amplification of streamwise fluctuations $\langle u_s^2 \rangle_0^+$ are pri-
 353 marily driven by viscoelastic energy absorption. This decoupling of velocity components
 354 confirms that the observed trends are a hallmark of polymer elasticity rather than a sec-
 355 ondary effect of viscosity reduction. By using the equivalent Newtonian inner scales for
 356 comparison, these results isolate the role of polymer-induced elastic stresses in restructuring
 357 the near-wall turbulence.

358 B. Accelerating flow

359 Developing BLs on the channel wall surfaces (see figure 4) were subjected to favourable
 360 PGs of varying strength within the converging region of the channel. In this study, the
 361 characteristics of the near-wall flow were investigated in the V-FPG FOV, highlighted in
 362 figure 4, over the flat surface using PIV. A zoomed-in view of the converging section is

Figure 7. Mean Reynolds stresses as functions of the wall-normal coordinate, n_0^+ , for fully developed C-FPG PAM solution flows: (a) 200 p.p.m. and (b) 400 p.p.m., each at three different Re_τ values (see table II). The corresponding water flow profiles from figure 5(b) are included as solid lines with matching colour codes for direct comparison. The horizontal axes, n_0^+ , are logarithmic. The profiles are normalised by their corresponding equivalent Newtonian $u_{\tau,0}$ and $\lambda_{v,0}$ values.

363 shown in figure 8, with the key streamwise locations indicated by the global coordinate x ,
 364 normalised by h_{in} . These locations mark the streamwise start and end points of the concave,
 365 inclined flat, and convex wall profiles of the curved surface.

Figure 8. Streamwise coordinates of key sub-flow regions within the pressure gradient section of the channel, normalised by the inlet height, $h_{in} = 8$ mm. The light orange rectangle highlights the interrogated V-FPG FOV shown in figure 4, stretched for clarity. Not to scale.

366 This section discusses the dynamics of developing BLs of pure water and PAM solution

367 flows upstream of the bump on the flat surface, where the flow strongly accelerates. The
 368 mean velocity and Reynolds stress fields obtained from PIV measurements were spatially
 369 averaged in windows of $\pm \Delta s \approx \pm 47 \mu\text{m}$ in the wall-parallel direction to reduce data noise
 370 while preserving the field gradients. As a result, the spatial resolution was reduced to $2 \Delta s \approx$
 371 $94 \mu\text{m}$, and the number of streamwise data points was halved from 71 to 35. The results
 372 presented in this section are confined to the acceleration region, $-0.71 h_{\text{in}} \leq s \leq -0.42 h_{\text{in}}$.
 373 No averaging was performed in the wall-normal direction, and the resolution in this direction
 374 remained unchanged at $\Delta n \approx 47 \mu\text{m}$.

375 1. Integral parameters

376 In channels with non-uniform, curved walls, the edge velocity $U_e(s)$ varies along the
 377 streamwise direction, and it is recommended that classical definitions of integral BL quan-
 378 tities to be generalised [40]. This can be achieved by expressing the mean velocity in terms
 379 of the spanwise vorticity. The corresponding equations are given in the Supplementary Ma-
 380 terial. This vorticity-based formulation has been successfully employed in DNS studies of
 381 flows over bumps [4, 46], where the high spatial resolution allows accurate computation of
 382 vorticity fields. In experimental investigations, even those using PIV, the spatial resolution
 383 is typically insufficient to capture vorticity reliably, as also noted by Maciel *et al.* [47]. The
 384 classical definitions were used to evaluate the BL parameters, and wherever applicable inte-
 385 gral quantities based on the generalised velocity were also evaluated for comparison and are
 386 discerned using a tilde symbol over the related variables.

387 Figure 9(a) illustrates the streamwise evolution of the boundary layer thickness, δ , and
 388 the generalised boundary layer thickness, $\tilde{\delta}$, both normalised by the inlet height h_{in} . In the
 389 Newtonian case (water), δ remains nearly constant at approximately $0.3h_{\text{in}}$. This stability
 390 indicates a well-defined inviscid core region that persists through the acceleration zone. The
 391 generalised thickness $\tilde{\delta}$ for water closely aligns with δ over the concave and inclined regions,
 392 showing only a slight divergence toward smaller values as the flow enters the convex section.

393 The introduction of polymers significantly alters the growth of the boundary layer and
 394 increases the discrepancy between the two definitions. In the 200 p.p.m. solution, the
 395 traditional thickness δ increases markedly, exceeding $0.5h_{\text{in}}$ over the convex wall. In contrast,
 396 the generalised thickness $\tilde{\delta}$ for the same concentration remains significantly lower, staying

397 below the mid-channel height with far less streamwise variation. For the 400 p.p.m. case, δ
398 initially shows lower values in the concave region but rises sharply toward the throat.

399 The values of $\tilde{\delta}$, derived from the generalised velocity approach (detailed in Section 3 of
400 the Supplementary Material), are represented as dashed lines in figure 9(a). Generally, $\tilde{\delta}$
401 exhibits a more dampened local variation across the convergence compared to the traditional
402 δ . Physically, the addition of polymers up to 200 p.p.m. results in a marginal increase in the
403 average generalised thickness, shifting from $\approx 0.25h_{\text{in}}$ to $\approx 0.30h_{\text{in}}$. However, increasing the
404 concentration to 400 p.p.m. leads to a more substantial expansion of the boundary layer,
405 with $\tilde{\delta}$ reaching $0.5h_{\text{in}}$.

406 In turbulent BLs, the displacement thickness δ^* and momentum thickness θ quantify the
407 effective reduction in flow area and momentum flux due to viscous effects, respectively. Their
408 ratio, the shape factor $H = \delta^*/\theta$, serves as a compact indicator of the BL state. Figure 9(b)
409 presents the streamwise evolution of both the traditional shape factor H (solid lines) and
410 the generalised shape factor \tilde{H} (dashed lines) at the highest tested flow rates.

411 The comparison between the classical and generalised profiles reveals a strong depen-
412 dence on both polymer concentration and local wall geometry. For the water flow and the
413 200 p.p.m. flow, \tilde{H} is consistently larger than the classical H throughout the convergence.
414 In the water case, the \tilde{H} profile appears as an amplified version of the classical profile. It is
415 important to note that the generalised velocity approach relies on the vorticity field. Cal-
416 culating derivatives from experimental PIV data inherently amplifies measurement noise,
417 which could lead to local variations in the profiles when compared to the classical definition.

418 A distinct behaviour was observed for the 400 p.p.m. solution. In the concave and
419 inclined flat regions, \tilde{H} is notably lower than the classical H . This reversal suggests that
420 at high polymer concentrations, the traditional definition may actually overestimate the
421 shape factor by failing to account for the modified vorticity field within the concave section.
422 Physically, the interaction between high elasticity and inward curvature likely restructures
423 the near-wall velocity profile such that the displacement effect, when viewed through the
424 generalised velocity approach, is less severe than the classical approach suggests.

425 For the water flow, H rises to ≈ 1.5 in the concave section, where inward curvature
426 destabilises the BL and enhances turbulence and mixing [48, 49] even as FPG tends to
427 stabilise it. Over the straight, inclined segment, absent curvature effects, FPG dominates
428 and maintains low H by reinforcing the log-law profile. In the convex region, outward

Figure 9. Streamwise evolution of (a) the BL thickness, δ , normalised by the inlet height, h_{in} , (b) the shape factor, H , and (c) the ratio of the local BL edge velocity, U_e , to the local mean streamwise velocity, U_b , in the converging region of the channel, where the flow accelerates. Results are shown for the highest tested flow rate of each working fluid. For reference, the results based on the generalised velocity are also shown as dashed lines. Legend entries indicate Re_{τ} of the fully developed C-FPG flows (see table II).

429 curvature suppresses turbulence and momentum transfer [50], counteracting overall channel
 430 convergence: streamlines spread out, locally decelerating the near-wall flow, weakening the
 431 velocity gradient, and driving H sharply upward toward separation-like behaviour.

432 The 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m. PAM solutions exhibit only mild streamwise variation in
 433 H (averaging ≈ 1.33 and ≈ 1.36 , respectively), with slight peaks over the concave section
 434 (figure 9b). The polymers' elasticity and the varying FPG stabilise the BL against curvature-
 435 induced disturbances, yielding a more uniform H profile through the acceleration region.

436 Figure 9(c) compares the streamwise evolution of the local edge-to-mean velocity ratio,
 437 U_e/U_b , for water and polymeric solutions at the highest tested flow rate. In this context,
 438 $U_e(s)$ is defined as the local maximum of the mean streamwise velocity $\langle U_s \rangle$ nearest to
 439 the wall, while $U_b(s)$ represents its wall-normal average across the BL. As detailed in the
 440 Supplementary Material, the absolute values may be shifted by uncertainties in wall and
 441 BL-edge detection, core distortion, and non-Newtonian effects. To facilitate the calculation
 442 of spatial gradients, a ninth-order polynomial was fitted to the $U_e(s)$ data.

443 Across all investigated cases, U_e/U_b exhibits a nearly linear increase throughout the
 444 convergence region, which is indicative of strong flow acceleration. For the water flow, the
 445 ratio reaches ≈ 1.19 at the throat ($s = -0.42 h_{\text{in}}$). Notably, the 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m.
 446 PAM flows achieve significantly higher peaks, reaching up to ≈ 1.35 . This occurs despite
 447 the fact that fully developed non-Newtonian flows typically exhibit lower U_e/U_b ratios in
 448 the range of 1.21–1.28. In the concave and inclined-flat segments, U_e/U_b initially falls below
 449 these typical values before rising sharply upon entering the convex region. This suggests that
 450 the interplay between viscoelasticity and spatially varying acceleration skews the velocity
 451 profile further, enhancing the U_e/U_b ratio beyond Newtonian levels (see § III B 2).

452 The velocity ratios derived from the generalised velocity approach, \tilde{U}_e/\tilde{U}_b (represented
 453 by dashed lines), fall consistently below the traditional U_e/U_b profiles over the entire con-
 454 vergence region. These generalised profiles demonstrate relatively lower local variation, with
 455 the discrepancy between the two methodologies becoming most pronounced in the convex
 456 region. Furthermore, the streamwise averages of the \tilde{U}_e/\tilde{U}_b profiles yield values of 1.12 ± 0.01 ,
 457 1.09 ± 0.02 , and 1.11 ± 0.03 for the water, 200 p.p.m., and 400 p.p.m. flows. This comparative
 458 stability of the generalised approach suggests it is less sensitive to the coordinate-dependent
 459 artefacts introduced by streamline curvature, particularly in the non-Newtonian cases.

460 Figure 10(a) presents the streamwise variations of the pressure coefficient,

$$c_p = \frac{P_e - P_0}{\frac{1}{2}\rho U_{b,0}^2}, \quad (10)$$

461 and the edge pressure gradient, dP_e/ds , for the highest Reynolds number of each fluid. Here,
 462 P_e is the pressure at the BL edge, $P_0 = 0$ is the reference pressure, and $U_{b,0}$ is the mean
 463 C-FPG velocity. Here, P_e is determined via the classical Bernoulli relation, assuming an
 464 irrotational core where elastic contributions to the total pressure are negligible in polymeric
 465 flows. This approximation is justified for dilute solutions in high-acceleration geometries,

466 where dynamic pressure changes significantly outweigh the first normal stress differences in
467 the low-shear core.

468 Throughout the convergence region, $c_p < 0$ and $dP_e/ds < 0$, indicating a continuously
469 varying FPG. The concave bump profile generates a strong FPG that persists over the
470 inclined flat wall and into the first half of the convex region. Beyond $s \approx -0.47 h_{\text{in}}$, dP_e/ds
471 weakens as the flow approaches the throat.

472 For the non-Newtonian PAM solutions, c_p and dP_e/ds exhibit similar trends (figure 10a).
473 In both 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m. cases, dP_e/ds remains nearly constant through the
474 concave section, intensifies (more negative) over the inclined wall, peaks in the convex region,
475 and then relaxes toward zero at the throat. The 400 p.p.m. flow shows a slightly stronger
476 peak magnitude than the 200 p.p.m. case.

477 Figure 10(b) compares the acceleration parameter K (equation 2) and FPG parameter
478 Δ_p (equation 1) for water and polymeric flows. In all cases, $K \gg 3 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\Delta_p < -0.025$,
479 confirming full relaminarisation under strong FPG. Both PAM solutions exhibit maxima in
480 $K(s)$ near the convex region onset at $s/h_{\text{in}} \approx -0.48$ and pronounced minima in Δ_p within
481 the upstream half of the inclined wall ($-0.60 < s/h_{\text{in}} < -0.57$).

482 The streamwise evolution of Δ_p reveals a distinct concentration-dependent behaviour.
483 While the profiles for water and the 200 p.p.m. solution remain relatively similar, the
484 400 p.p.m. case exhibits a pronounced peak within the inclined flat-wall region. This
485 localisation is attributed to the absence of curvature-induced disturbances in this segment,
486 allowing the strong FPG to maximise polymer chain extension and turbulence suppression.

487 As Δ_p scales with u_τ^{-3} (see equation 1), the sharp rise in the 400 p.p.m. profile reflects a
488 significant local reduction in the friction velocity, u_τ , as the flow approaches a relaminarised
489 state. In the adjacent concave and convex regions, the presence of streamline curvature
490 maintains higher wall shear stress, which dampens the Δ_p values. The discrepancy between
491 the 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m. cases suggest that a critical concentration is required to
492 sufficiently suppress turbulent stresses in this non-equilibrium flow, leading to the non-linear
493 amplification of the pressure parameter seen at the highest concentration.

Figure 10. Streamwise changes of the (a) pressure coefficient c_p (see equation 10) and BL edge’s pressure gradient dP_e/ds , and (b) the acceleration parameter K (equation 2) and FPG parameter Δ_p (equation 1) for the highest flow rates of the tested water and polymeric solution flows. The legend shows Re_{τ} values of the fully-developed C-FPG flows (see table II).

494 2. Mean statistics

495 As discussed in § III B 1, unlike fully-developed C-FPG turbulent flows with streamwise-
 496 invariant statistics, V-FPG flows (see figure 8) exhibit strong spatial variations. Local BL
 497 parameters vary with the streamwise coordinate s , depending on the local FPG strength
 498 and wall curvature. The isolated impact of PAM additives on mean statistics, such as
 499 velocity and Reynolds stresses, in fully developed C-FPG flows was examined in § III A 2.
 500 The PG parameter profiles in figure 10(b) indicate that both Newtonian and non-Newtonian
 501 accelerating flows undergo relaminarisation, where the combined influence of viscoelasticity
 502 and pressure gradient acts to suppress turbulence.

503 This section extends the analysis by examining the influence of V-FPG on the local
 504 mean statistics of Newtonian and non-Newtonian polymeric flows. High-resolution PIV
 505 measurements were performed in the convergence region, where the flow accelerates (see
 506 figure 8). The analysis focuses on the top flat wall, where the BLs experience pressure
 507 gradients induced by the non-flat lower wall. The convergence region is divided into concave,
 508 inclined flat, and convex segments based on the lower wall curvature. Spatial distributions
 509 of the mean velocity field were acquired at the mid-span of the channel ($z = 0$). Streamwise
 510 variations in the accelerating mean velocity and Reynolds stress profiles are presented for
 511 water and 200 p.p.m. and 400 p.p.m. solutions and their dynamics are analysed in detail.

512 Figure 11(a) shows inner-normalised wall-parallel velocity profiles under a continuous,
 513 spatially varying FPG in the convergence region (see figures 8 and 10a). Just upstream of
 514 the concave section, all profiles deviate from the standard log-law, indicating non-equilibrium
 515 conditions. At $s/h_{\text{in}} = -0.80$, the $Re_{\tau,0} = 245$ profile falls below the log region, while for
 516 higher $Re_{\tau,0}$, stronger FPG shifts the profile above the log-law, though with a reduced slope
 517 compared to $\kappa^{-1} \approx 2.44$. At the start of the inclined flat wall ($s/h_{\text{in}} = -0.60$), the strong
 518 PG shifts the velocity profile well above the standard log-law. With increasing $Re_{\tau,0}$, this
 519 deviation grows, the viscous sublayer thickens, and the profile resembles that of a laminar
 520 flow. Near the throat entrance, reduced shear further elevates the profile above the log-law.

Figure 11. Wall-normal variations of the mean wall-parallel velocity profiles, normalised by the local inner scales, at eight selected wall-parallel positions for accelerating (a) water, (b) 200 p.p.m., and (c) 400 p.p.m. flows over the flat surface of the channel's convergence region.

521 Figure 11(b) presents the inner-normalised velocity profiles of the 200 p.p.m. PAM flow
 522 along the convergence region. All profiles collapse onto $\langle U_s \rangle^+ = n^+$ in the viscous sublayer.
 523 As the flow enters the concave region, the profiles are suppressed below the log-law due to

524 strong FPG. In the latter half, as FPG weakens, friction slightly increases and the profiles
 525 lift toward the log-law. At higher flow rates, local shear decreases, shifting profiles above the
 526 log-law. Approaching the throat, FPG vanishes and convex curvature increases wall shear,
 527 pushing the profiles back below the log-law. Even at the highest tested $Re_{\tau,0}$, elevated
 528 profiles retain slopes close to κ^{-1} and do not approach the ultimate profile.

529 Figure 11(c) presents the inner-normalised mean velocity profiles of the accelerating
 530 400 p.p.m. PAM flow. All profiles collapse onto the linear sublayer near the wall. As the
 531 flow advances through the second half of the concave region and into the inclined flat wall,
 532 $\langle U_s \rangle^+$ rises steadily, in some cases exceeding the ultimate profile. These elevated profiles lack
 533 a logarithmic shape, consistent with flows approaching MDR [19]. At $s/h_{\text{in}} = -0.57$, near
 534 the centre of the inclined region, this deviation is most pronounced, where the combined
 535 effects of strong FPG and viscoelasticity significantly reduce wall shear stress, pushing the
 536 profile well above the log law. Approaching the convex region, the flow stabilises and the
 537 profiles shift below the standard log law, particularly in the outer layer.

538 Figure 12(a) shows the wall-normal distribution of the inner-normalised Reynolds shear
 539 stress, $-\langle u_s u_n \rangle^+$, for water flows across the convergence region. At the entrance, profiles
 540 resemble those of fully developed C-FPG flows but with reduced peaks. In the first half of
 541 the concave region, the strong FPG suppresses turbulence, lowering the shear stress. As the
 542 FPG weakens in the second half, wall shear gradually decreases and $-\langle u_s u_n \rangle^+$ intensifies,
 543 peaking near $s/h_{\text{in}} = -0.60$, with greater amplification at higher $Re_{\tau,0}$. This elevated stress
 544 persists to $s/h_{\text{in}} = -0.57$, before the FPG regains strength, damping turbulence again
 545 through the inclined flat and early convex regions. Beyond $s/h_{\text{in}} = -0.48$, where the FPG
 546 almost diminishes, turbulence production increases, shifting the shear stress profiles upward.

547 Figure 12(b) presents the inner-normalised Reynolds shear stress profiles for the acceler-
 548 ating 200 p.p.m. PAM flow. As the flow moves into the latter half of the concave region,
 549 turbulence production near the wall intensifies, which is driven by the diminishing FPG and
 550 the destabilising influence of wall curvature. Yet, this rise is short-lived. Over the convex
 551 section, while the weaker FPG would normally permit increased turbulence, the stabilising
 552 effect of convex curvature tempers this growth. Consequently, the $-\langle u_s u_n \rangle^+$ profiles over
 553 the convex region remain subdued relative to upstream profiles.

554 Near the throat ($s/h_{\text{in}} = -0.42$), where both pressure gradient and curvature effects
 555 fade, turbulence production resurges, as evident from the elevated shear stress levels. This

Figure 12. Wall-normal variations of the mean Reynolds shear stress profiles, normalised by the local inner scales, at eight selected wall-parallel positions for accelerating (a) water, (b) 200 p.p.m., and (c) 400 p.p.m. flows over the flat surface of the channel’s convergence region.

556 general trend is echoed across all tested flow rates. However, increasing the flow rate reveals
 557 a marked suppression of Reynolds shear stress, highlighting the compounded damping effects
 558 of viscoelasticity, FPG, and curvature. The peak stress consistently occurs around $s/h_{\text{in}} =$
 559 -0.65 , midway through the concave section.

560 Further comparison of dimensional shear stress profiles, provided in figure 8(a,b) of the
 561 Supplementary Material, reinforces this attenuation. In the range $1 \leq n \leq 2$ mm, the
 562 200 p.p.m. solution at $Re_{\tau,0} = 154$ exhibits streamwise shear stress levels nearly 80% lower
 563 than the water flow at $Re_{\tau,0} = 286$. This substantial reduction underscores the significant
 564 role of polymer-induced viscoelasticity in suppressing turbulence in accelerating flows.

565 Figure 12(c) shows the normalised mean Reynolds shear stress profiles for the 400 p.p.m.
 566 PAM solution flow across the convergence region. For $Re_{\tau,0} = 122$, $-\langle u_s u_n \rangle^+$ values in the
 567 outer layer are on the order of $\mathcal{O}(0.1)$. The higher flow rate exhibits a similar trend, with

568 only slight changes in magnitude.

569 A comparison of the highest flow rates for the two PAM concentrations reveals a tur-
570 bulence production reduction of approximately 67%, while matching $Re_{\tau,0} \approx 140$ condi-
571 tions yield a maximum decrease of around 76%. Dimensional shear stress profiles for the
572 400 p.p.m. flows, presented in figure 8(c) of the Supplementary Material, demonstrate a
573 maximum attenuation near 89% within the $1 \leq n \leq 2$ mm range compared to water flows
574 at the same conditions. These results underscore the substantial turbulence suppression due
575 to viscoelasticity at elevated polymer concentrations and flow rates.

576 While mean Reynolds shear stress is strongly attenuated across the outer boundary layer,
577 a notable peak emerges near the wall as the flow approaches the throat region. However,
578 high measurement uncertainties in this near-wall zone obscure the exact peak location, which
579 is estimated to lie within $10 < n^+ < 20$ or $0 < n/\delta < 0.2$.

580 Another intriguing local phenomenon in the accelerating flows is the appearance of neg-
581 ative mean Reynolds shear stress regions in the outer layer, often termed ‘counter-gradient’
582 stresses [51]. Similar observations were made by Pandey *et al.* [52] in DNS of channel
583 flows under non-uniform body forces. These zones arise as the FPG, coupled with polymer
584 additives, relaminarises the flow and suppresses turbulence production.

585 As shown in figure 13(a), at the convergence region entrance ($s/h_{\text{in}} = -0.80$), the inner-
586 normalised wall-parallel Reynolds stresses closely match those of the C-FPG flows. Entering
587 the concave region, $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$ slightly increases for the higher flow rates, then gradually decreases
588 over the first half, aligning with the entrance profile. Near the concave region end ($s/h_{\text{in}} =$
589 -0.60), $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$ rises sharply due to a relative drop in skin friction. Over the inclined flat wall,
590 it lowers again and reaches a minimum at $s/h_{\text{in}} = -0.48$. Approaching the throat, friction
591 decreases once more, amplifying $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$, especially at higher flow rates. Overall, increasing
592 $Re_{\tau,0}$ correlates with a significant rise in $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$, consistent with wall stress variations.

593 Figure 13(b) shows that all $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$ profiles exhibit pronounced near-wall peaks, while
594 remaining nearly constant across the outer layer. At $s/h_{\text{in}} = -0.65$, mid-concave region,
595 $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$ rises above other positions for all flow rates. Downstream toward the throat, as the
596 FPG weakens and friction increases, $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$ relaxes toward entrance flow levels. Similarly,
597 figure 13(c) shows that in the 400 p.p.m. flows, spatial variations in FPG strength lead to
598 varying $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$ intensities. Entering the convex region, strong curvature stabilises the flow,
599 and outer-layer profiles align with the entrance flow. Throughout the convergence region,

Figure 13. Wall-normal variations of the mean wall-parallel Reynolds stress profiles, normalized by the local inner scales, at eight selected wall-parallel positions for accelerating (a) water, (b) 200 p.p.m., and (c) 400 p.p.m. flows over the flat surface of the channel's convergence region.

600 $\langle u_s^2 \rangle^+$ peaks strongly near $n^+ \approx 12$, with intensity varying streamwise.

601 Figure 14(a) illustrates the normalised wall-normal Reynolds stress profiles for acceler-
 602 ating water flows. The intensity of $\langle u_n^2 \rangle^+$ varies markedly across the convergence region and
 603 between flow rates. At lower flow rates, larger local friction result in lower normalised stress
 604 levels. For the $Re_{\tau,0} = 286$ case, $\langle u_n^2 \rangle^+$ initially amplifies as the flow enters the acceleration
 605 region, then attenuates through the first half of the concave region. In the second half, it
 606 increases sharply, exhibiting a local minimum at $n^+ \approx 30$. Over the first half of the inclined
 607 flat wall, $\langle u_n^2 \rangle^+$ remains nearly constant, before decreasing through the second half and into
 608 the middle of the convex region. In the second half, the profile amplifies again, and at the
 609 throat entrance, another minimum appears near $n^+ \approx 30$, but at a relatively higher level.

610 Figure 14(b) presents the inner-normalised wall-normal Reynolds stress profiles for the
 611 200 p.p.m. flows. Turbulent intensity increases over the second half of the concave region,

612 with $\langle u_n^2 \rangle^+$ reaching elevated levels. A distinct feature of these profiles is the presence of
 613 local minima downstream of the concave section. As the flow enters the inclined flat wall
 614 region, $\langle u_n^2 \rangle^+$ drops abruptly to a minimum within $20 < n^+ < 25$, then gradually rises.
 615 Similar trends appear at other post-concave positions, whereas profiles within the concave
 616 region do not exhibit such minima.

Figure 14. Wall-normal variations of the mean wall-normal Reynolds stress profiles, normalized by the local inner scales, at eight selected wall-parallel positions for accelerating (a) water, (b) 200 p.p.m., and (c) 400 p.p.m. flows over the flat surface of the channel's convergence region.

617 Figure 14(c) illustrates the inner-normalised wall-normal Reynolds stress profiles for the
 618 400 p.p.m. PAM flows. Across all tested conditions, the combined influence of the FPG and
 619 viscoelasticity markedly suppresses fluctuations in the buffer layer ($20 < n^+ < 30$). At the
 620 entrance to the convergence region, however, $\langle u_n^2 \rangle^+$ remains slightly elevated in the outer
 621 layer. As the flow progresses into the second half of the concave section ($s/h_{in} = -0.65$),
 622 the profile exhibits a notable 'knee point' at $n^+ \approx 35$, where the gradient of $\langle u_n^2 \rangle^+$ reverses
 623 direction, a phenomenon previously identified by Baskaran *et al.* [5]. Here, the stress drops

624 nearly linearly from a high near-wall value to the knee point, before rising more gently in
625 the outer region. This feature persists up to the onset of the convex wall. Upon entering the
626 convex section, near-wall stresses ease further. Flows at higher rates follow a comparable
627 pattern, though the knee becomes increasingly compressed in the wall-normal direction and
628 the gradient changes more abruptly.

629 While the pressure gradient parameters K and Δ_p suggest a state of relaminarisation,
630 the near-wall dynamics in the polymeric flows indicate a transition to a complex viscoelastic
631 regime rather than a simple return to a Newtonian laminar state. The presence of stream-
632 line curvature over the bump fillets ($r_c = 1$ mm) introduces hoop stresses, extra normal
633 stresses acting along curved streamlines, that can interfere with the polymer stretching-
634 relaxation cycle. An order-of-magnitude analysis (see § 5 of Supplementary Material) using
635 the Pakdel-McKinley criterion, $M = \sqrt{(\delta/r_c)Wi}$, yields a stability parameter $M \approx 46.5$.
636 This value is well above the established thresholds for purely elastic instabilities, suggesting
637 that curvature-induced stresses are physically significant.

638 Although the strong stabilising influence of the FPG prevents a complete transition to
639 purely elastic turbulence, the 400 p.p.m. solution exists in a quasi-relaminarised state where
640 inertia-driven Reynolds stresses are nearly eliminated, yet elastic stresses maintain significant
641 wall-parallel fluctuations. This interpretation is physically supported by the mean velocity
642 profiles, which exceed Virk's ultimate profile in the accelerating region. Ultimately, the
643 V-FPG suppresses the traditional turbulent bursting mechanism while the local curvature
644 maintains the polymers in an active, fluctuating state, providing a unique experimental
645 observation of a viscoelastic BL dominated by pressure-gradient-enhanced elasticity.

646 IV. CONCLUSIONS

647 This study investigated the modification of turbulence by drag-reducing polymers in
648 developing boundary layers subjected to both constant and spatially varying favourable
649 pressure gradients (FPGs). Using high-resolution microscopic PIV in a converging-diverging
650 channel, the behaviour of pure water was comparatively analysed against 200 p.p.m. and
651 400 p.p.m. PAM solutions.

652 Measurement uncertainties were rigorously quantified, with mean velocity errors below
653 0.2% and near-wall random uncertainties limited to 4.5%. The non-Newtonian characteris-

654 tics of the polymeric solutions were accurately captured using the Carreau-Yasuda model,
655 providing a robust framework for interpreting the observed flow physics.

656 **Acceleration and Curvature in Newtonian Flow**

657 In the Newtonian cases, the transition from a constant-FPG (C-FPG) to a spatially
658 varying FPG (V-FPG) regime triggered distinct relaminarisation processes, evidenced by
659 acceleration parameters exceeding $K \approx 3 \times 10^{-6}$ and $\Delta p < -0.025$. The flow stability was
660 locally governed by the interplay between pressure gradients and wall curvature: concave
661 surfaces coupled with weak FPG destabilised the BL, while convex surfaces and strong accel-
662 eration promoted stabilisation. These non-equilibrium effects caused significant deviations
663 from the classical law-of-the-wall and shifted the turbulent stress distributions accordingly.

664 **Polymer Dynamics and Physical Mechanisms**

665 The distinct statistical deviations observed in the polymeric flows are fundamentally
666 rooted in the non-linear response of polymer chain dynamics to spatially varying accel-
667 eration. While C-FPG flows achieve a steady-state extension, the V-FPG region triggers a
668 more aggressive stretching-relaxation cycle. In the inclined flat-wall segment, the pure con-
669 vective acceleration (V-FPG) maximises polymer extension, forcing the chains into a highly
670 aligned state that effectively absorbs energy from wall-normal velocity fluctuations (u_n).
671 This mechanism explains the near-total collapse of Reynolds shear stress and the elevation
672 of mean velocity profiles above Virk's ultimate profile. Conversely, in the concave segment,
673 the competing influences of destabilising curvature and acceleration likely hinder optimal
674 chain extension, leading to less pronounced turbulence dampening compared to purely ac-
675 celerating segments.

676 **Pressure Gradient Effects on Polymeric Flows**

677 At the highest tested flow rates, DR of 31.7% and 38.8% was achieved in C-FPG 200 and
678 400 p.p.m. PAM solutions. While maximum DR was not reached under constant gradients,
679 the V-FPG acceleration zone further attenuated turbulence. The 200 p.p.m. profiles devi-

ated around the log law depending on local curvature, while 400 p.p.m. profiles exceeded the ultimate profile under strong V-FPG, with no discernible logarithmic region. Compared to water, dimensional Reynolds shear stress was reduced by up to 80% in 200 p.p.m. and 89% in 400 p.p.m. flows.

Summary and Implications

These results confirm that viscoelastic polymers significantly restructure near-wall turbulence, particularly when subjected to the non-linear strain rates of a V-FPG. While the FPG independently promotes flow stability, the addition of PAM introduces an elastic mechanism that drives the boundary layer toward a relaminarised state much earlier than in Newtonian flows. This study provides the first spatially resolved experimental dataset of polymer-induced turbulence modification under non-uniform acceleration, serving as a high-fidelity benchmark for the validation of future viscoelastic simulations and the design of drag-optimised curved surfaces.

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